

WPscan – Discovering the Vulnerabilities and Enumerating Users of WordPress Sites with Autotor for IP Spoofing

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Abstract—WPscan is an open source WordPress security scanner. You can use it to scan your WordPress website for known vulnerabilities in popular WordPress plugins and themes. Since it is a black box scanner, it almost copies an action of a real attacker. This means that for conducting the tests, it does not depend on any access to your WordPress dashboard or source code. To put it another way, if WPscan can find a flaw in your WordPress website, an attacker can too. An attacker trying to either guess or confirm that something they are targeting exists on the target system is commonly termed as Enumeration.

Some of the most commonly enumeration scans that WPscan does during a scan are:

- Detection of versions of WordPress core, plugins and themes,
- Looks for wp-config.php backups or other database exports that are open to the public.
- Counting the number of users and administrators.

Keywords—WPscan, WordPress, vulnerability, AutoTor, IP Spoofing.

I. INTRODUCTION

WPscan usually scans a WordPress website for known vulnerabilities in popular WordPress plugins and themes.

What we are trying to do here is WordPress username enumeration and weak password cracking (aka brute force attack) in a WordPress site hosted in localhost.

As already discussed, WPscan can enumerate WordPress users as part of its enumeration features. However, WPscan can also go one step further by attempting to crack weak passwords. This is useful to do in order to audit your WordPress website for weak credentials. Password cracking is achieved by passing WPscan a password dictionary of your choice.

The WPscan tool performing its job in online wordpress site can lead to much serious offences, because after all what we are doing is intrusion into someone else's property. But by accompanying the Auto Tor tool which is not a pre-installed tool we can do this safely because it will be very hard for anyone to trace the source IP which gets changed in every couple of seconds.

II. FEATURES

- WPscan will check the version of WordPress that is installed as well as any bugs that may be present.
- What themes are mounted, as well as any bugs that may be associated with them.
- Enumeration of user names
- Password brute forcing for users with poor passwords.
- wp-config.php files are backed up and publicly available.
- What plugins are mounted, and are there any bugs associated with them?
- Database dumps that could be made public.
- Complete Path Disclosing
- Verify the WP-Cron is turned on.
- Verify that the readme file for WordPress is present.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

WPscan come pre-installed with Kali Linux. But for we need to manually install AutoTor for dynamic IP spoofing. By following the below steps user enumeration with dynamic spoofing of IP can be done.

Step 1: Download and install the WPscan and Auto Tor if it is not installed.

Step 2: Start WPscan.

Step3: Type --url http://localhost:81/wordpress (*URL of the site*)

Fig. 1. Output for step 3 (WPscan command)

Step 4: Now type in the command to enumeration of users “wpscan --url http://localhost:81/wordpress/ -e u”.

Fig. 2. Output for step 4 (Enumerating users)

Step 5: Type in the next command “wpscan --url http://localhost:81/wordpress/ -P rockyou.txt --usernames root” (Brute forcing password for root). rockyou.txt is a wordlist dictionary provided by kali linux for weak password bypassing.

Fig. 3. Output for step 5 (Password bruteforcing)

Here, we got the password for the username “root”. Now we can simply go to https://localhost:81/wordpress /wp-login.php and enter these login credentials to get onto the admin dashboard of the site.

Step 6: If we want to brute force an online site, we may use Auto Tor which is an IP spoofing application.

Use this command to invoke AutoTor: “python3 autoTOR.py”.

Step 7: Start Auto Tor and note the SOCKES address.

Fig. 4. Output for step 7 (Enumerating users)

Step 8: Now go to the browser and change the proxy settings.

In the configure proxy access section, select Manual proxy configuration and enter the SOCKES address provided by Auto Tor as the host SOCK and click OK.

Fig. 5. Output for step 8 (Replacing SOCKES host)

Step 9: Now go to Auto Tor and set the time for each interval for spoofing.

Step 10: Now follow steps 2 to 5 by entering the desired URL.

Advantages & Disadvantages

Advantages :

- Open Source
- Simple and easy to use.
- Untraceable because of dynamic IP.

Disadvantages:

- Only Weak passwords can be cracked in user enumeration unless we use a more wide dictionary

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

We know that there are only 3 password attempts in an online wp-admin page. But by including our guesses into the rockyou.txt file we can simply ignore this.

For instance, if the username is Rahul, we can guess rahul@123, Rahul\$436 etc as possible passwords and edit it to the rockyou.txt we can look for password matching endlessly and make the referring dictionary (txt file) broad.

IV. RESULT

The positive output of the above command is as follows:

```
(+) Enumerating Config backups (via Passive and Aggressive Methods)
Checking Config Backups - Time: 00:00:00 <=====
[!] No Config Backups Found.

[+] Performing password attack on Xnlrpc against 1 user/s
[SUCCESS] - root / xbox360
Trying root / butterfly! Time: 00:00:05 <=====

Valid Combinations Found:
| Username: root, Password: xbox360

[!] No WPVulnDB API Token given, as a result vulnerability data has not been output.
[!] You can get a free API token with 50 daily requests by registering at https://wpvuln.com/users/sign-up

[+] Finished: Mon Dec 7 10:43:27 2020
[+] Requests Done: 955
[+] Cached Requests: 32
[+] Data Sent: 484.158 KB
[+] Data Received: 671.689 KB
[+] Memory used: 1.012 GB
[+] Elapsed time: 00:00:16
root@kali:~#
```

Fig. 6. Successful fetch of username and password

IP spoofing in Auto Tor terminal is done as follows.

Enter the time to change IP in seconds and enter the number of times you IP is to be changed (ie, if you enter the first value as 10 and seconds as 20, after 10 seconds the IP address will get changed and this will be repeated 20 times.)

During this spoofing process we can securely scan for vulnerabilities in wordpress sites hosted online.

Now we can effortlessly do the same process of WPscan by inputting an actual wordpress site URL with same steps above.


```
Auto Tor
V 2.1

from mrFD
http://facebook.com/ninja.hackerz.kurdish/

change your SOCKS to 127.0.0.1:9050

[+] time to change Ip in Sec [type=60] >> 10
[+] how many time do you want to change your ip [type=1000]for infinte ip change type [0] >>200
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2605:6400:30:fca::2
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c2:2::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2001:470:1d:3b0::ac:ce55
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c2:2::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c2:2::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c2:2::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c2:1::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c0:16c:16::1
[+] Your IP has been Changed to : 2a0b:f4c1:2::243
```

Fig. 7. AutoTor changing IP with specific configuration

V. CONCLUSION

WPscan is an open source WordPress security scanner. You can use it to scan your WordPress website for known vulnerabilities within the WordPress core, as well as popular WordPress plugins and themes.

Since it is a WordPress black box scanner, it mimics a real attacker. This means it does not rely on any sort of access to your WordPress dashboard or source code to conduct the tests. In other words, if WPscan can find a vulnerability in your WordPress website, so can an attacker.

A person who has the knowledge of how WPscan works can keep his/her wordpress sites attack-free. We know about the two factor authentication techniques used in wordpress admin page. If features like these are enabled it is almost impossible for an intruder to let himself into the admin dashboard.

VI. REFERENCE

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